

INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS: GAMIFIED PLATFORMS.

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Abstract. *The purpose of the thesis is to analyze the effectiveness of integrating digital technologies into the English language learning process in secondary schools. The paper examines the advantages of using online platforms, interactive applications, and digital resources, and explores the possibilities of using gamified online platforms (Kahoot, Wordwall, Quizlet) in English language learning in secondary schools. It is shown that game mechanics (competition, instant feedback, and elements of gamification) increase students' motivation and help them reinforce their vocabulary and grammar knowledge. At the same time, the following limitations were identified: superficial learning, a lack of productive activities, and dependence on technical conditions. The article concludes that it is necessary to integrate game resources into combined learning models.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, gamification, digital technologies, English, high school, Kahoot, Wordwall, Quizlet. educational platforms.*

Introduction

The development of information and communication technologies (ICT) has a significant impact on the education system, including the teaching of foreign languages. The current generation of students is part of the "digital generation," which is accustomed to using online resources, multimedia, and mobile devices. As a result, there is an increasing need to revise the teaching methods for English, including the integration of digital tools into educational practices. Gamification has become a leading trend in the digital transformation of education. The use of game mechanics allows to increase the motivation of schoolchildren, make the process of learning a foreign language more exciting and closer to the digital environment familiar to teenagers. For teaching English, this is especially relevant: game formats help to retain attention, stimulate the repetition of material and form a positive attitude towards learning the language.

Among the most actively used resources are:

- Gamified platforms (Kahoot, Wordwall, Quizlet)
- Mobile apps (Duolingo, LingQ, EWA)
- Video platforms and online courses (BBC Learning English, TED-Ed, Coursera)
- Interactive workbooks and textbooks (Oxford Learn, Pearson MyEnglishLab)

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Gamified platforms:

Kahoot. An online service for creating quizzes and surveys in real time. It is used to reinforce vocabulary, grammar, and cultural knowledge. Its strengths include a competitive element and instant feedback. However, it requires a stable internet connection and is more suitable for quick knowledge checks rather than in-depth analysis.

Wordwall. A platform with a wide range of game templates, including crosswords, match-ups, wheel of fortune, and mazes. Teachers can easily adapt to the right vocabulary and grammar. The resource is convenient both for front-end work in the classroom and for individual practice at home. Limitation — The free version limits the number of tasks created.

Quizlet. It is based on flashcards, which can be used to memorize words, collocations, and expressions. It supports "game", "written test", and "listening" modes. The strong point is the ability for students to edit word sets together. The disadvantage is excessive attention.

Mobile applications:

Duolingo. Based on the principle of "small steps": daily mini-lessons of 5-10 minutes, gamification (experience points, series, levels). Useful for consolidating vocabulary and grammar in a playful format. However, exercises are often disconnected from real communication, which limits the depth of learning.

LingQ. The main advantage is working with authentic texts and audio, where students mark unfamiliar words and immediately see translations. Suitable for developing reading and listening skills. Limitation - the interface requires a certain degree of independence and digital literacy, which may be difficult for younger students.

EWA. The app combines interactive dialogues, movie/book excerpts, and word repetition exercises. It features an attractive visual design and a large collection of materials. It is suitable for self-practice. Limitation - some content is only available in the paid version.

Video platforms and online courses:

BBC Learning English. One of the most popular free resources that includes video and audio materials, texts, and exercises. Useful for practicing listening, learning relevant vocabulary, and getting acquainted with the British version of English.

TED-Ed. Short educational videos on various topics, accompanied by subtitles and exercises. Used for developing critical thinking, retelling skills, and discussion. A limitation is that some of the videos may be difficult for students to understand without adaptation.

Coursera. A platform for university-level online courses. For students, specialized courses in Academic English, Speaking & Writing can be useful. However,

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the level of assignments is often higher than the average school level, which requires teacher support.

Interactive workbooks and textbooks:

Oxford Learn. Electronic versions of Oxford University Press textbooks with exercises, voiceovers, automatic checking, and interactive training. Supports adaptability and tracking of student progress.

Pearson MyEnglishLab. A platform with exercises that are closely integrated into Pearson's educational courses. Benefits include automatic checking, built-in error correction tips, and teacher analytics. Limitations include being tied to specific curricula and requiring a license.

The digital environment promotes critical thinking and media literacy, which is especially important in an era of information abundance. Working with online sources, analyzing videos, podcasts, forums, and social media, students develop the skills to interpret and filter information.

Thus, digitalization in English teaching is not a universal solution, but with the right approach, it can significantly improve the quality and accessibility of education.

Comparison table: advantages and challenges

Resource category	Benefits	Challenges / Restrictions
Gamified platforms (Kahoot, Wordwall, Quizlet)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased motivation and engagement through a game-like format - Quick knowledge assessment - Opportunities for collective interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires a stable internet connection - Superficial learning with an excessive focus on speed - Limited opportunities for productive speech activities
Mobile applications (Duolingo, LingQ, EWA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accessibility "anytime, anywhere" - Building a habit of regular practice - Variety of content (vocabulary, reading, audio) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The risk of fragmented knowledge - Limited real-time communication - Some features are only available in paid versions
Video platforms and online courses (BBC Learning English, TED-Ed, Coursera)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to authentic materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overloaded with complex content without adaptation

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Resource category	Benefits	Challenges / Restrictions
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of listening, critical thinking, and intercultural competence - Opportunities for in-depth study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires a high level of autonomy - Often aimed at an adult audience
Interactive workbooks and textbooks (Oxford Learn, Pearson MyEnglishLab)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration with the curriculum - Automatic verification and analytics of progress - Support for adaptive learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Require a license and access to the platform - Limited flexibility outside of the course - Dependence on the school's technical infrastructure

Gamified platforms (Kahoot, Wordwall, Quizlet):

The use of gamified services has become one of the most popular areas in English language teaching in secondary schools. Kahoot allows you to conduct dynamic quizzes and surveys, turning knowledge testing into an exciting competition. Wordwall offers a variety of game templates, from crosswords and matchmaking to interactive mazes that help consolidate vocabulary and grammatical structures. Quizlet is based on flashcards and supports different vocabulary training modes: testing, listening, matching, which is especially useful for expanding active and passive vocabulary.

Advantages:

- building sustainable motivation through the game element;
- developing competitiveness and teamwork;
- instant feedback and the ability to track progress;
- flexibility in use (frontally, in pairs, individually, at home).

Challenges and limitations:

- superficial learning of the material with an emphasis on speed rather than depth;
- insufficient work with productive skills (speaking, writing), as the tasks mainly train receptive skills;
- dependence on an internet connection and the availability of devices;
- the risk of "over-gamification", when the game begins to dominate the learning goal.

Thus, gamified platforms are a powerful tool for increasing student engagement, but they require careful use and combination with other forms of work to avoid superficial memorization.

Conclusion

The use of gamified platforms (Kahoot, Wordwall, Quizlet) in teaching English at secondary schools demonstrates significant potential in increasing students' motivation and engagement. Game mechanics allow for the transformation of routine tasks – vocabulary repetition, consolidation of grammatical structures, knowledge control – into emotionally charged and dynamic activities. Such resources are especially effective in front-line work in the classroom, in organizing mini-competitions, and in practicing the material learned.

At the same time, the analysis has shown that the didactic value of gamified services has limitations. Their use is primarily focused on receptive skills and memory training, while productive types of speech activity (speaking, writing) are developed to a lesser extent. In addition, an excessive focus on game elements can shift the emphasis from the educational goal to the competitive process, which reduces the depth of material acquisition.

Thus, gamified platforms cannot be considered as a universal tool that can replace traditional forms of learning. Their effectiveness is achieved through balanced integration into the learning process:

- inclusion at the beginning and end of the lesson for activation and summation;
- use as a tool for formative assessment;
- combination with project and communicative activities;
- teacher development of tasks aimed not only at reproduction, but also at meaningful application of language material.

In the future, gamified technologies can become an important component of a comprehensive digital ecosystem for teaching English, if they are viewed as an addition to the communicative approach rather than an alternative. Their methodologically sound use allows not only to maintain students' motivation, but also to create a positive experience of interacting with a foreign language in a digital environment.

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